

Antecedents and Loyalty of Foreign Tourists towards Attractions in Bangkok Metropolitan Area, Thailand

Authors : Arunroong Wongkungwan

Abstract : This study aimed to investigate the influence of selected antecedents, which were tourists' satisfaction towards attractions in Bangkok, perceived value of the attractions, feelings of engagement with the attractions, acquaintance with the attractions, push factors, pull factors and motivation to seek novelty, on foreign tourist's loyalty towards tourist attractions in Bangkok. By using multi stage sampling technique, 400 international tourists were sampled. After that, Semi Structural Equation Model was utilized in the analysis stage by LISREL. The Semi Structural Equation Model of the selected antecedents of tourist's loyalty attractions had a correlation with the empirical data through the following statistical descriptions: Chi-square = 3.43, df = 4, P- value = 0.48893; RMSEA = 0.000; CFI = 1.00; CN = 1539.75; RMR = 0.0022; GFI = 1.00 and AGFI = 0.98. The findings indicated that all antecedents were able together to predict the loyalty of the foreign tourists who visited Bangkok at 73 percent.

Keywords : antecedent, Bangkok, foreign tourists, loyalty, tourist attractions

Conference Title : ICEMBIT 2014 : International Conference on Economics, Management of Business, Innovation and Technology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : June 29-30, 2014